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NON-PLAQUE-INDUCED GINGIVAL DISEASES

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Abstract: Although most gingival diseases are caused by the dental plaque on the tooth surfaces, those not caused by plaque accumulation, while less common, can have adverse consequences for patient health. Such non-plaque-induced gingival lesions are often manifestations of systemic conditions, but may also signify pathological changes in the gingival tissues. Current classification, based on the lesion etiology, includes genetic/developmental disorders; specific infections; inflammatory and immune conditions and lesions; reactive processes; neoplasms; endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases; traumatic lesions; and gingival pigmentation, which should serve as a guideline for dentists and periodontists when establishing diagnoses, formulating treatment plans, or referring such patients for treatment.

Key words: classification, gingival diseases, periodontal disease

Introduction

Human gingiva may exhibit several non-plaque-induced pathological lesions, which are often manifestations of systemic conditions, but may also signify pathological changes in the gingival tissues. Although these lesions are not directly caused by plaque, their clinical course may be affected by plaque accumulation and subsequent gingival inflammation [1].

The understanding of etiology and pathogenesis of oral diseases has considerably increased in recent years due to the scientific advances. A review of non-plaque-induced gingival lesions was presented at the 1999 International Workshop for a Classification of Periodontal Diseases and Conditions [1]. This classification was subsequently revised, whereby in the latest generally accepted version from 2017 (Table 1.) some non-plaque-induced gingival diseases and conditions that were not covered by the previous systematization are described (Table 2.) [1,2].

Table 1. Classification of periodontal diseases and conditions 2017

PERIODONTAL HEALTH, GINGIVAL DISEASES AND CONDITIONS	PERIODONTITIS	OTHER CONDITIONS AFFECTING THE PERIODONTIUM
Periodontal health and Gingival health Gingivitis: Dental plaque-induced Gingival diseases: Non-plaque-induced	Necrotizing periodontal diseases Periodontitis Periodontitis as a manifestation of systemic diseases	Systemic diseases or conditions affecting the periodontal tissues Periodontal abscesses and endodontic-periodontal lesions Mucogingival deformities and conditions Traumatic occlusal forces Tooth and prosthesis related factors

Table 2. Non-plaque-induced gingival diseases and conditions

1. Genetic/developmental disorders
 - 1.1. Hereditary gingival fibromatosis (HGF)
2. Specific infections
 - 2.1. Bacterial origin
 - 2.2. Viral origin
 - 2.3. Fungal
3. Inflammatory and immune conditions and lesions
 - 3.1. Hypersensitivity reactions
 - 3.2. Autoimmune diseases of skin and mucous membranes
 - 3.3. Granulomatous inflammatory conditions
4. Reactive processes
 - 4.1. Epulides
5. Neoplasms
 - 5.1. Premalignant
 - 5.2. Malignant
6. Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases
 - 6.1. Vitamin deficiencies
7. Traumatic lesions
 - 7.1. Physical/mechanical insults
 - 7.2. Chemical (toxic) insults
 - 7.3. Thermal insults
8. Gingival pigmentation
 - 8.1. Gingival pigmentation/melanoplakia
 - 8.2. Smoker's melanosis
 - 8.3. Drug-induced pigmentation
 - 8.4. Amalgam tattoo

1. GENETIC/DEVELOPMENTAL ABNORMALITIES

1.1. Hereditary gingival fibromatosis (HGF)

Hereditary gingival fibromatosis (HGF) is an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern characterized by fibrous gingival overgrowth that can cover the teeth completely or partially, preventing eruption in many cases [3].

2. SPECIFIC INFECTIONS

2.1. Infections with bacterial origin

Necrotizing periodontal disease

Necrotizing gingivitis (NG), *necrotizing periodontitis* (NP), and *necrotizing stomatitis* (NS) are severe inflammatory periodontal diseases caused by bacterial infection (*Treponema spp.*, *Selenomonas spp.*, *Fusobacterium spp.*, *Prevotella intermedia* and others) in patients with specific underlying risk factors, such as poor oral hygiene, smoking, stress, inadequate nutrition or compromised immune status. The term “gingivitis” is used for lesions involving gingival tissue only, without loss of periodontal attachment. Central necrosis of the papillae may result in considerable tissue destruction that would lead to crater formation. If loss of attachment is established, the diagnosis is NP. NS is diagnosed when lesions with ulceration extending >1.0 cm from the gingival margin, including tissue beyond the mucogingival junction, is present [4].

2.2. Viral origin

Coxsackie virus

Coxsackie viruses may cause herpangina and hand-foot-and-mouth disease. While herpangina does not involve gingiva, hand-foot-and-mouth disease is a common contagious vesicular viral disease affecting skin and oral mucosa, including gingiva. The lesions, which present as small vesicles that leave fibrinous coated ulcers upon rupture, are primarily seen in children [5].

HSV-1 and HSV-2

HSV-1 usually causes oral manifestations, whereas HSV-2 primarily leads to anogenital infections and only occasionally oral infections [6].

Primary herpetic infection (Herpetic gingivostomatitis) occurs mostly in infants and manifests as the formation of few or many vesicles, which rupture, coalesce, and leave fibrin-coated ulcers, often of irregular extension. The gingiva is erythematous and swollen. After the primary infection, the latent virus can be reactivated in 20–30% of patients, usually in adulthood. Recurrent intraoral herpes simplex lesions typically occur on keratinized mucosa of hard palate and attached gingiva [6].

Varicella-zoster virus

Primary varicella-zoster virus infection causes varicella (chicken pox), mainly in children. When the virus is reactivated in adulthood, it causes herpes zoster which manifests as unilateral lesions on the skin or oral mucosa following the distribution of an infected nerve. If the second or third branch of the trigeminal nerve is involved, skin lesions may be associated with intraoral lesions (including gingival lesions) or intraoral lesions may occur alone. Emergence of lesions may be preceded by pain and paresthesia. When lesions initially appear, they are in form of vesicles, which soon rupture and leave fibrin-coated small ulcers, often coalescing to irregular forms up to the midline [7].

Human papilloma virus (HPV)

More than 100 types of HPV have been identified, and at least 25 types have been detected in oral lesions. Benign oral lesions associated with HPV infection include squamous cell papilloma, condyloma acuminatum, verruca vulgaris, and focal epithelial hyperplasia. These lesions are mostly asymptomatic, exophytic papillomatosis, verrucous or flat lesions. Histopathology of removed lesions is required for a definitive diagnosis [1].

2.3. Fungal origin

Candidiasis

Candidiasis is the most common fungal infection of the oral mucosa and is mainly caused by *C. albicans*. Less common species include *C. glabrata*, *C. krusei*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. guilliermondii* and *C. dubliniensis*. Candidiasis can be acute or chronic, with pseudomembranous, erythematous and hyperplastic (plaque-like/nodular) clinical presentations [8]. While candidal infection can affect any part of the oral mucosa, gingival lesions are rare in otherwise healthy individuals. Gingival candidal infection typically manifests as redness of the attached gingiva, often with a granular surface. Pseudomembranous candidiasis is characterized by whitish creamy plaques resembling milk curds which can be wiped away, leaving behind an erythematous mucosal surface that is prone to bleeding. Nodular gingival lesions are uncommon and present as slightly elevated nodules of a white or reddish color. “Linear gingival erythema” described in the 1999 International Workshop, associated with HIV infection, is now generally regarded as gingival candidiasis and has therefore been removed from this classification [1].

3. Inflammatory and immune conditions and lesions

3.1. Hypersensitivity reactions

Contact allergy

Oral mucosal manifestations of hypersensitivity may be caused by dental restorative materials, dentifrices, mouthwashes, and certain foods, and are typically classed as Type IV hypersensitivity reactions (contact allergy) involving redness and sometimes lichenoid lesions [1].

Plasma cell gingivitis

Plasma cell gingivitis is a relatively rare condition that usually occurs on the anterior maxillary and mandibular gingiva. It manifests as extreme redness, swelling, and gum tissue enlargement with propensity for bleeding (Picture 1.). While the disease etiology remains unclear, its presentation is mostly attributed to nonspecific inflammatory reaction to certain foodstuffs or ingredients in oral hygiene products [9].

Picture 1. Plasma cell gingivitis

Erythema multiforme (EM)

EM is an acute immune-inflammatory disorder of the oral mucosa with unknown etiology in most cases. However, it is posited to be an immunologic hypersensitivity reaction mediated by T-lymphocytes. It can be triggered by infections, particularly those of herpetic type, and some drugs. EM symptoms vary, from mild erythema and erosion to painful ulcerations, and typically extend to the anterior part of the mouth and lips [7].

3.2. Autoimmune diseases of skin and mucous membranes

Pemphigus vulgaris

PV is an autoimmune vesiculobullous disease of skin and mucous membranes often involving the oral mucosa and initially presenting as oral lesions in 60% of these cases. It results in the formation of intraepithelial bullae on otherwise normal skin or mucosa due to autoantibodies directed against desmosome-associated protein antigens. Gingival localization of PV usually manifests as desquamative gingivitis and/or as vesiculobullous lesions of the free and attached gingiva which, after bullae rapidly rupture, leave erosions [7].

Pemphigoid

Pemphigoid is a group of mucocutaneous disorders caused by autoantibodies toward antigens of the basement membrane, resulting in detachment of the epithelium from the connective tissue. If only mucous membranes are affected, it is denoted as mucous membrane pemphigoid (MMP). The subepithelial lesions of MMP most frequently involve the oral mucosa and typically manifests as desquamative lesions of the gingiva presenting as intensely erythematous areas. Lesions may present as intact vesicles of the gingival or other mucosal surfaces, but more frequently they appear as nonspecific-appearing erosions [7].

Lichen planus

Lichen planus is a common mucocutaneous disease frequently affecting the gingiva and manifesting as an inflammatory reaction toward an unidentified antigen in the basal epithelial layer/basement membrane zone. Six types of clinical manifestation have been described—reticular, papular, ulcerative, bullous, plaque, and erythematous type. The lesions are usually bilateral, often involve the gingiva, and present as desquamative gingivitis, causing pain and discomfort during eating and toothbrushing. Because lichen planus has been shown to exhibit premalignant potential, it is important to diagnose, treat, and follow the affected patients through regular oral examinations [7]. In a recent randomized controlled trial, a tailored plaque-control regime was shown to be beneficial in reducing symptoms of gingival lichen planus and improving patients' overall quality of life [10].

Lupus erythematosus (LE)

LE is a group of autoimmune disorders that result in the production of a great variety of autoantibodies, particularly antinuclear antibodies. Two major forms are described in extant literature—discoid LE (DLE) and systemic LE (SLE). Approximately 20% of the patients with LE develop oral lesions. DLE is a mild chronic form, which involves skin and mucous membranes, sometimes including the gingiva as well as other parts of the oral mucosa. A typical lesion presents as a central atrophic area with small white dots surrounded by irradiating fine white striae. It is estimated that about 8% of patients with DLE will develop SLE, and this progression is usually diagnosed through the emergence of ulcerations [7].

3.3. Granulomatous inflammatory conditions (orofacial granulomatosis)

Various systemic conditions like tuberculosis, Crohn's disease (CD), sarcoidosis and Melkersson–Rosenthal syndrome can result in persistent enlargement of the soft tissues in the oral cavity and the facial region. In recognition of this fact, in 1985, Wiesenfeld introduced the term orofacial granulomatosis (OFG) to make a distinction between these manifestations and granulomas that occur in the absence of any recognized systemic condition. Although OFG etiology is still unknown, several causes have been suggested, including infection, genetic predisposition, and allergy. The clinical symptoms include labial enlargement, cobblestone appearance of the oral mucosa, linear ulceration, and gingival overgrowth. There is still no consensus on whether OFG is a distinct clinical disorder, or an initial presentation of CD or sarcoidosis, or even an allergic reaction [11, 12].

4. Reactive processes

4.1. Epulides

Epulis is a term often applied to exophytic processes originating from the gingiva. Usually patients do not present with any symptoms, although the reactive processes are thought to cause an

exaggerated tissue response to limited local irritation or trauma, and are classified according to the histological findings. True epulides include Fibrous epulis, Calcifying fibroblastic granuloma, Pyogenic granuloma (Picture 2.) and Peripheral giant cell granuloma (or central). In a recent study involving 2,068 cases of reactive lesions of the oral cavity, the attached gingiva (with 1,331 cases, or 64.36% of the total sample) was found to be the most frequently affected location [13].

Picture 2. Pyogenic granuloma

5. Neoplasms

5.1. Premalignant

Leukoplakia

Oral leukoplakia is defined as a predominantly white lesion of the oral mucosa that cannot be attributed to any other definable type. The exact cause of leukoplakia is unknown, but heavy smoking and alcohol use are the main risk factors [7]. Lesions are generally asymptomatic with smooth, corrugated, or verrucous surface. They cannot be rubbed off and occur most frequently on the buccal mucosa, mandibular gingiva, tongue, and mouth floor. Leukoplakia can be of homogeneous or non-homogenous subtype. The prevalence of malignant transformation in leukoplakia ranges from 0.13% to 34%. Larger lesions and those of non-homogenous type are associated with a greater risk of malignant transformation than homogenous leukoplakia [14].

5.2. Malignant

Squamous cell carcinoma

Squamous cell carcinoma of the gingiva represents about 20% of intraoral carcinomas and occurs most frequently in the mandibular premolar and molar regions. The resulting lesions often present as painless exophytic masses, red and white speckled patches, or non-healing ulcerations involving the keratinized gingiva. Although lesions typically occur in edentulous areas, they may also be present at sites around dentition. Mobility of adjacent teeth is common, and invasion of the underlying alveolar bone occurs in approximately 50% of cases [15].

Leukemia

Leukemia results from the proliferation of a clone of abnormal hematopoietic cells. It is classified based on clinical behavior (acute or chronic) and the primary hematopoietic cell line affected (myeloid or lymphoid). Oral lesions occur in both acute and chronic leukemia but are more

common in the acute form. The signs and symptoms are diverse and include pallor of the oral mucosa, pain, petechiae and ecchymosis, gingival bleeding, and gingival swelling due to leukemic cell infiltration. Deep punched-out ulcerations and necrosis on gingiva and tooth mobility can also be present [7].

Lymphoma

Lymphoma is an umbrella term for describing tumors of the lymphoid system and may originate from B-lymphocyte and T-lymphocyte cell lines. Its main two types are Hodgkin lymphoma and non-Hodgkin lymphoma. Non-specific gingival swelling may be the first manifestation of non-Hodgkin lymphoma, mimicking a periodontal abscess or pyogenic granuloma. In contrast, oral manifestations of Hodgkin lymphoma are extremely rare [7].

6. Endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic diseases

6.1. Vitamin deficiencies

Vitamin C deficiency - scurvy

Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) is necessary for various metabolic processes, such as formation of collagen, which is a primary structural protein in the human body. As reduced plasma ascorbic acid concentration in scurvy causes changes in connective tissue metabolism, it results in gingival bleeding, swelling and ulceration, as well as a compromised immune response [11].

7. Traumatic lesions

7.1. Physical/mechanical insults

Frictional keratosis, Toothbrushing-induced gingival ulceration, Factitious injury (self-harm)

Inappropriate toothbrushing can be injurious to the gingival tissues. Limited physical trauma from brushing may result in gingival hyperkeratosis, a white leukoplakia-like lesion referred to as frictional keratosis. In cases of more extensive toothbrushing damage, symptoms vary from superficial horizontal gingival lacerations to major loss of tissue resulting in gingival recession. A characteristic finding in these patients is extremely good oral hygiene and/or cervical tooth abrasion. Self-inflicted injury to the gingival tissue is more common in young patients, in whom lesions may present as unusual tissue damage with ulceration in areas that can easily be reached by fingers and instruments [16].

7.2. Chemical (toxic) insults

Toxic chemical products may result in surface sloughing or ulceration which can be related to the use of chlorhexidine, acetylsalicylic acid, cocaine, hydrogen peroxide, or dentifrice detergents. These lesions are reversible and resolve after removing the toxic influence. Injury to the gingival tissue may also be caused by incorrect use of endodontic materials that may be toxic to the gingiva, including paraformaldehyde or calcium hydroxide, which may give rise to inflammation, ulceration, and necrosis of the gingival tissue if the cavity sealing is insufficient [17].

7.3. Thermal insults

Thermal injuries are usually caused by consumption of hot fluids and may affect any part of the oral mucosa, including the gingiva. The lesion is erythematous with sloughing of a coagulated surface and may sometimes present as ulceration, petechiae, or erosions. Vesicles may also occur in some cases [6].

8. Gingival pigmentation

8.1. Gingival pigmentation/melanoplakia

Physiologic melanin pigmentation presents as brownish-to-black diffusely pigmented areas on the attached gingiva, most often in persons with a dark skin complexion. If there is a sudden or gradual onset of diffuse mucosal pigmentation in adulthood, other sources should be considered, such as endocrine disturbances (Addison's disease) or syndromes (Albright syndrome, Peutz-Jegher syndrome) [7].

8.2. Smoker's melanosis

Cigarette smoking is the primary etiological factor in melanocytic pigmentation of the oral mucosa. It typically presents as brownish areas on the mandibular anterior gingiva. Melanosis gradually improves or may completely resolve upon cessation of smoking [7].

8.3. Drug-induced pigmentation

Antimalarial agents, such as chloroquine diphosphate and hydroxychloroquine sulfate, that are used for treating dermatologic and rheumatologic disorders can cause hyperpigmentation of the oral mucosa. These medications can stimulate melanin production by melanocytes and/or can cause hemosiderin deposition, potentially facilitating focal microscopic hemorrhage. Nevertheless, the exact mechanisms involved are not yet established. These alterations are generally reversible and improvements are typically noted as soon as the medication is discontinued [18].

Minocycline is a semisynthetic tetracycline and its black degradation product may be deposited in tissues. Long-term use of minocycline is associated with pigmentation of the alveolar bone and teeth. When changes in bone are viewed through relatively thin overlying mucosa, the gingiva may appear gray, especially in the maxillary anterior region. True minocycline-induced soft tissue pigmentation is much less common [19].

8.4. Amalgam tattoo

Pigmentation of the oral mucosa due to the use of amalgam fillings is frequently seen in patients affected by gingiva and alveolar mucosa. The lesion presents as a flat well-defined bluish or grayish discoloration. Introduction of amalgam particles into the gingival connective tissue through breaks in the epithelium can occur during tooth extraction or restorative procedures [11].

Conclusion

Non-plaque-induced gingival diseases cannot be resolved by dental plaque control. Current classification, based on the lesion etiology, should serve as a guideline for dentists and periodontists when establishing diagnoses, formulating treatment plans, or referring such patients for treatment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Holmstrup P, Plemons J, Meyle J. Non-plaque-induced gingival disease. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2018;45(Suppl 20):S28–S43.
- [2] Caton JG, Armitage G, Berglundh T, Chapple ILC, Jepsen S, Kornman KS, et al. A new classification scheme for periodontal and peri-implant diseases and conditions – Introduction and key changes from the 1999 classification. *J Periodontol*. 2018;89(Suppl 1):S1–S8.
- [3] Pastor PJA, Vera PJB, Illueca FMA, Pizarro MC. Hereditary gingival fibromatosis: Characteristics and treatment approach. *J Clin Exp Dent*. 2017 Apr; 9(4): e599–e602.
- [4] Horning GM, Cohen ME. Necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis, periodontitis, and stomatitis: Clinical staging and predisposing factors. *J Periodontol*. 1995;66:990–8.
- [5] Aswathyraj S, Arunkumar G, Alidjinou EK, Hober D. Hand, foot and mouth disease (HFMD): Emerging epidemiology and the need for a vaccine strategy. *Med Microbiol Immunol*. 2016;205:397–407.
- [6] Newman MG, Takei HH, Klokkevold PR, Carranza FA. Newman and Carranza's Clinical Periodontology 13th edition. Elsevier. Philadelphia, 2019.
- [7] Greenberg MS, Glick M, Ship JA. Burket's oral medicine 11th edition. BC Decker Inc, Hamilton 2008.
- [8] Tarcin BG. Oral Candidosis: Aetiology, Clinical Manifestations, Diagnosis and Management. *MÜSBED* 2011;1(2):140–8.
- [9] Djurić M, Veljović T, Gušić I, Mirnić J, Vučković N, Petrović Dj. *Vojnosanit Pregl* 2019;76:81–5.
- [10] Stone SJ, McCracken GI, Heasman PA, Staines KS, Pennington M. Cost-effectiveness of personalized plaque control for managing the gingival manifestations of oral lichen planus: A randomized controlled study. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2013;40:859–67.
- [11] Cawson RA, Odel EW. Cawson's essentials of oral pathology and oral medicine. Eight edition. Elsevier. Edinburgh, 2008.
- [12] Grave B, McCullough M, Wiesenfeld D. Orofacial granulomatosis — A 20-year review. *Oral Dis*. 2009;15:46–51
- [13] Naderi NJ, Eshghyar N, Esfahanian H. Reactive lesions of the oral cavity: A retrospective study on 2068 cases. *Dent Res J (Isfahan)*. 2012;9:251–5.
- [14] Dionne KR, Warnakulasuriya S, Zain RB, Cheong SC. Potentially malignant disorders of the oral cavity: Current practice and future directions in the clinic and laboratory. *Int J Cancer*. 2015;136:503–15.
- [15] Bharanidharan R, Dineshkumar T, Raghavendhar K, Kumar AR. Squamous cell carcinoma of the gingiva: A diagnostic enigma. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol*. 2015;19:267.
- [16] Rawal SY, Claman LJ, Kalmar JR, Tatakis DN. Traumatic lesions of the gingiva: A case series. *J Periodontol*. 2004;75:762–9.
- [17] De Bruyne MA, De Moor RJ, Raes FM. Necrosis of the gingiva caused by calcium hydroxide: A case report. *Int Endod J*. 2000;33:67–71.
- [18] de Andrade BA, Fonseca FP, Pires FR, et al. Hard palate hyperpigmentation secondary to chronic chloroquine therapy: Report of five cases. *J Cutan Pathol*. 2013;40:833–8.
- [19] Treister NS, Magalnick D, Woo SB. Oral mucosal pigmentation secondary to minocycline therapy: Report of two cases and a review of the literature. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*. 2004;97:718–25.